

ASSOCIATION BETWEEN CORPORATE FINANCIAL PERFORMANCE AND ESG RATINGS OF PUBLIC COMPANIES: AGGREGATE REGRESSION ANALYSIS**Svetlin Minev***Assistant Professor**University of Economics – Varna**Knyaz Boris I Blvd 77, 9002 Varna, Bulgaria***Abstract**

ESG ratings have become a primary tool to evaluate how sustainably public companies operate and how they perform on non-financial metrics. Most of the studies so far have focused on how ESG factors influence corporate financial performance (CFP), while the reverse relationship has received less attention. This article analyses whether and to what extent corporate financial performance affects ESG ratings. The study is based on a cross-sectional regression analysis using ESG ratings from LSEG Data & Analytics and a range of CFP indicators. The results show a statistically significant but moderate relationship between CFP and ESG ratings, with company size and operating efficiency having a positive impact, while market multipliers and ownership structure show a negative relationship.

Keywords: ESG ratings, corporate financial performance, sustainability, regression analysis, non-financial reporting

1. Introduction

The topics of corporate social and environmental responsibility and responsible investment have been present in the literature for several decades, but have gained particular relevance in the last two decades [1]. Some of the main reasons are increased regulatory pressures, societal expectations, and the growing role of sustainable finance [2]. The concept of ESG as a tool for assessing the long-term sustainability of companies is increasing in popularity and as a result, the link between ESG ratings and CFP has become an important topic in academic research. [3]. Nevertheless, the majority of empirical studies examine how ESG factors influence financial performance (ESG - CFP) and have mixed and often contradictory results, with positive, negative, or mixed relationships observed [2]. Some studies have found a positive relationship between ESG and metrics such as ROA, Tobin's Q, and market capitalization, while others have found negative effects or no statistically significant relationship [4]. Significantly less attention has been paid to the inverse relationship – whether CFP affects ESG performance. Existing research on this relationship is limited in scope and often focuses on individual sectors or specific ESG components [5]. This creates a research gap in understanding whether good financial standing is a prerequisite for higher ESG ratings.

This study focuses on this less explored direction of the relationship between ESG and CFP. The main objective is to examine whether companies with better financial performance achieve higher ESG ratings, which would support the theoretical arguments of the slack resources theory and the resource dependence theory [6]. The analysis is carried out at the aggregate level in order to assess the CFP - ESG relationship. The present study extends this literature by combining a broad set of financial indicators - covering size, profitability, market valuation, and ownership structure - in a single aggregate cross-sectoral model applied to a global large-cap sample, thus enabling systematic comparison of predictor patterns across dimensions not previously examined jointly.

2. Theoretical Framework and Literature Review

The two-way relationship between ESG and CFP can be explained by several complementary theoretical frameworks. Stakeholder theory assumes that companies that balance the interests of different groups strengthen their reputation and create the conditions for sustainable growth [7]. Resource dependence theory emphasizes the strategic importance of external resources and relationships, suggesting that by implementing effective ESG policies, firms can reduce risk and dependence on the external environment and improve their long-term sustainability [6].

Signaling theory considers ESG disclosure as a signal under conditions of information asymmetry. Companies with better ESG performance have an incentive to disclose more extensive and higher-quality information, while companies with poor performance may limit or distort disclosures, which increases the risk of greenwashing [8]. Agency theory focuses on principal-agent conflicts and suggests that good corporate governance (the G component) reduces agency costs and improves efficiency and sustainable growth [9]. According to the theory of shareholder supremacy, maximizing shareholder wealth is a top priority of the firm, and making this priority a social norm is the biggest barrier to implementing ESG principles [10].

ESG ratings are used for assessing the performance of companies in the areas of environmental protection, social responsibility and corporate governance, as well as the risks associated with their sustainable development. One of the main objectives in calculating them is to reduce the information asymmetry between the company and stakeholders and to make it easier for investors to identify companies in good financial condition and at the same time distinguished by high responsibility to society and the environment [11]. The most popular are the ESG ratings of specialized agencies such as MSCI, Morningstar Sustainability, Bloomberg, and LSEG Data & Analytics, but due to the application of different methodologies, there are discrepancies between the rating providers [12].

The results of various studies on the relationship between ESG ratings and corporate financial performance suggest that the impact of ESG practices is mixed. The majority of studies have found a positive impact of ESG on CFP [2], but there is still no universally accepted model to conclusively confirm this relationship. In most cases, the observed correlations are weak, and there are many studies that show a mixed or even negative relationship [13]. Empirical studies analyzing the impact of CFP on ESG are significantly fewer. Some found a positive relationship, especially in terms of company size and profitability, while others did not find a statistically significant relationship or found negative effects in the short term [5], highlighting the need for further research.

3. Data and Methodology

The initial sample includes companies with a market capitalization exceeding USD 2 billion as of 31 March 2025. Financial and market data are primarily extracted from Yahoo Finance via Python (yfinance, pandas). ESG ratings are obtained from LSEG Data & Analytics due to their broad coverage and a 0–100 scale. The dependent variable in the regression model is the overall ESG rating. The independent variables include indicators of company size (market capitalization), profitability (ROA, operating and net margin), market valuation (P/S and P/B), five-year share returns, ownership structure (insider and institutional ownership), and the Piotroski F-score. The regression model is specified as follows:

$$TotalESG = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \ln(MCap) + \beta_2 ROA + \beta_3 OM + \beta_4 NM + \beta_5 5ypf + \beta_6 P/B + \beta_7 P/S + \beta_8 IndrO + \beta_9 InstO + \beta_{10} P_F + \varepsilon$$

where the independent variables are defined as follows:

- ln(MCap) - Natural logarithm of the company’s market capitalization
- ROA - Return on assets

- OM - Operating margin
- NM - Net margin
- 5ypf - Five-year return on stocks
- P/B - Price-to-book ratio
- P/S - Price-to-sales ratio
- IndrO - Insider ownership
- InstO - Institutional ownership
- P_F - Piotroski F-score

During data processing, companies without an ESG rating or key CFP indicators were removed. Missing values accounted for less than 5% of observations per variable and were replaced with values from StockAnalysis.com and FINVIZ.com, verified manually for consistency. After all exclusions, the final sample comprised 748 companies (68 per GICS sector). The pre-processing is made through winsorization, log transformation of market capitalization, and standardization of independent variables using z-scores. Fractional logit and beta regression were considered given the 0–100 bounded scale of ESG ratings; however, OLS with robust standard errors was retained as the primary specification due to its interpretability and given that scores are not concentrated near the boundaries. The analysis is conducted at the aggregate level without sector fixed effects, which is a deliberate design choice to estimate average cross-sector associations.

4. Results

At the aggregate level, the regression model is statistically significant ($F = 28.79, p < 0.01$) and explains approximately 27% of the variation in ESG ratings ($R^2 = 0.2711$). The Breusch–Pagan test confirms the presence of heteroscedasticity ($p < 0.01$), therefore coefficient significance is interpreted using robust standard errors. The VIF values do not indicate problematic multicollinearity (maximum ≈ 2.23). Six of the independent variables are statistically significant at the 5% level. The results are presented in Table 1.

Table 1

OLS Regression Results (Dependent variable: Total ESG rating, N = 748)

Variable	Coef.	Std. Error	t	p > t
Const.	63.29	0.54	116.26	–
ln(MCap)	+6.15	0.59	9.84	0.0000
P/S	–4.80	0.65	–7.18	0.0000
IndrO	–4.38	0.55	–5.92	0.0000
5ypf	–1.89	0.56	–3.12	0.0019
OM	+2.99	0.80	2.95	0.0033
InstO	–1.59	0.57	–2.84	0.0046
P_F	+1.01	0.56	1.68	0.0928
NM	–1.14	0.80	–1.15	0.2516
ROA	–0.47	0.63	–0.76	0.4481
P/B	–0.38	0.58	–0.57	0.5682

Fractional logit and beta regression were considered given the 0–100 bounded scale of ESG ratings; however, OLS with robust standard errors was retained

as the primary specification due to its interpretability and given that scores are not concentrated near the boundaries.

Market capitalization has a positive effect ($\beta \approx +6.15$), consistent with the fact that larger companies have wider resource and organizational capacity to implement and report on ESG policies. OM also has a positive effect ($\beta \approx +2.99$), suggesting that operational efficiency supports ESG engagement. The P/S ratio has a negative and significant effect ($\beta \approx -4.80$), as does the five-year return ($\beta \approx -1.89$), suggesting that growth expectations and strong stock market performance do not automatically translate into higher ESG ratings. Insider ownership has a negative effect ($\beta \approx -4.38$), while institutional ownership also has a negative but weaker effect ($\beta \approx -1.59$). The Piotroski F-score, ROA, and P/B are not statistically significant at $\alpha = 0.05$.

5. Discussion

The empirical results suggest that corporate financial performance has a statistically significant relationship with ESG ratings, but this relationship is moderate. At the aggregate level, the explanatory power of the model is approximately 27%, which is realistic for ESG models since a significant part of the variation in ratings is determined by non-financial factors and methodological features of ESG assessment. This is consistent with observations from meta-analyses that average correlations between ESG and CFP are often low [2].

The positive effect of company size is one of the most stable results and supports the slack resources logic and resource dependence theory. Large companies have the capacity to invest in ESG policies, and are under pressure from regulators, the media and the investors. The negative relationship between P/S and ESG can be interpreted as an indication that growth expectations and high market valuations often coincide with business strategies aimed at expansion and innovation, which are not always combined with prioritizing ESG. The negative effect of the 5 years return also suggests that strong stock market performance is not a condition for high ESG ratings. The most interesting result is the negative effect of institutional ownership. The institutional investors are seen as carriers of ESG pressures, but empirical measurement here probably captures their heterogeneity: passive funds, short-term institutional strategies, and mechanical index following can weaken the expected effect. It is also possible that high institutional ownership is more common in companies where focus is on valuation and growth rather than ESG as a management priority [14].

The regression model employed is cross-sectional and therefore does not allow for definitive causal inference and the possibility of reverse causality cannot be excluded. The findings should be interpreted as documenting systematic correlations rather than causal effects. ESG ratings are also based on provider-specific methodologies and inevitably involve a degree of uncertainty, which may add noise to the analysis results [12]. A notable limitation is the absence of sector fixed effects. ESG practices vary substantially across industries and some of the explained variance may partly reflect sector differences rather than CFP effects per se. Analysis examining whether the CFP–ESG association varies by sector represents an important avenue for future research.

6. Conclusion

The present study provides empirical evidence of a statistically significant relationship between corporate financial performance and ESG ratings of public companies at the aggregate level. The results suggest that better financial performance, creates favorable conditions for higher ESG performance, but does not automatically guarantee it. At the same time, market valuations and ownership structures have a more complex and often negative impact on ESG ratings, highlighting the limited role of purely financial factors in explaining sustainable corporate behavior. ESG ratings are formed under the influence of a wide range of non-financial factors, including the regulatory environment, corporate culture, and societal pressure. The findings contribute to the academic debate on the two-way relationship between ESG and CFP and suggest that financial performance should be viewed as a necessary but not sufficient condition for achieving high ESG standards [15]. Future research could further enhance understanding of this relationship by incorporating panel data, sector controls, and causal identification strategies.

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